

Sethian Gnostic

By Brian Alt, Indiana University

Entry tags: Christian Traditions, Roman Religions, Early Christianity, Heresy, Religious Group, Abrahamic

Sethian gnostics – also referred to by scholars as “classic gnostics” or simply “the gnostics” – represent a sect within early Christianity that existed from the second through the fourth century CE. Most of what we know about this group derives from the discovery of the Nag Hammadi collection of Coptic manuscripts, which dates to around 350 CE, but this information is supplemented by various heresiological writings by early proto-orthodox theologians, most significantly Irenaeus, who wrote around 180 CE. The name Sethian is applied to the sect by modern scholars because of its self-identification with the biblical Seth, son of Adam. “Gnostics” comes from the Greek word *gnōstikoi* (roughly, “those who know”), which some scholars consider to be a label the Sethians applied to themselves. Social information about the Sethians must be inferred from the textual evidence, which contains a number of features used to characterize them: (1) a complex cosmogonic myth based in part on a creative revision of Genesis and Plato’s *Timaeus*, (2) a strong sense of group identity and in-group language as the “seed (or offspring) of Seth,” and (3) a ritual of baptism sometimes called a ritual of “five seals.” Very little is known of the daily life or organizational structure of the Sethians. They shared with other Christians certain theological traditions, some scripture, and an ascetic lifestyle. Some features of the Sethian myth include: (1) an ineffable divine first principle called the Parent or Invisible Spirit; (2) a second principle called Barbelo; (3) a series of four luminaries, also called aeons or realms, named Harmozel, Oroiael, Daveithai, and Eleleth; (4) the emanation of a number of additional aeons, the last of which is named Wisdom (Sophia in Greek); (5) a craftsman (*dēmiourgos* in Greek) named Ialdabaoth, who steals divine power from his mother (Wisdom) to create the visible cosmos based on intelligible paradigms while remaining ignorant of the divinities higher than him; (6) the creation of seven, twelve, and/or 365 rulers of the material world who themselves create human beings and the remainder of the material world; (7) a dramatic struggle resulting in some of humanity being given Ialdabaoth’s pilfered power as a spark of divinity; (8) these human beings are the offspring of Seth, sealed by a special baptismal ritual, while the offspring of Cain remain under the power of the ignorant demiurge and his minions. (9) Where the human Jesus appears in the versions of this myth, he is variously identified with a preexistent Anointed One (Greek *christos*), a preexistent Word (Greek *logos*), a preexistent Seth, or Barbelo. Individual Sethian texts contain some but not all of the elements of this myth. As such, the category “Sethian Gnostic” can be understood as a polythetic class, i.e. it contains a number of non-essential characteristics but lacks an essential (*sine qua non*) characteristic. Some scholars, notably John D. Turner, have reconstructed a “literary history” of these texts based on textual developments within this mythic framework. The complex emanation scheme of the Sethian myth reveals an involvement with the Middle Platonic philosophical speculation of the time, which has been compared to such thinkers as Philo of Alexandria and Numenius of Apamea.

Date Range: 100 CE - 400 CE

Region: Alexandria and the Nile, Rome, Antioch and environs, etc.

Region tags: Europe, Southern Europe, Italy, Africa, Northern Africa, Egypt, Rome, Eastern Mediterranean

Regions are based on Bentley Layton, *The Gnostic Scriptures* (1987) pp. 10-11.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Brakke, David. *The Gnostics: Myth, Ritual, and Diversity in Early Christianity*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2010.
- Source 2: Turner, John D. *Sethian Gnosticism and the Platonic Tradition*. Quebec: Presses de l'Université Laval, 2001.
- Source 3: Layton, Bentley. *The Gnostic Scriptures*. New York: Doubleday, 1987.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://www.helsinki.fi/teol/pro/gnosti/eng_gnosticism/sethian.html
- Source 1 Description: An introduction to the Sethian gnostics maintained by Professor Antti Marjanen.
- Source 2 URL: <https://shwep.net/podcast/michael-williams-on-the-trouble-with-gnosticism/>
- Source 2 Description: Professor Michael Williams discusses the problems with the category "Gnosticism" and covers the scholarly views for and against "Sethian" as an alternative.
- Source 3 URL: <https://gnosticismexplained.org/the-classic-gnostics-sethians/>
- Source 3 Description: An introduction to the Classic (Sethian) gnostics written by Daniel McCoy.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://gnosis.org/naghamm/nhl.html>
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.earlychristianwritings.com/irenaeus.html>

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Most of what we know about this group derives from the discovery of the Nag Hammadi collection of Coptic manuscripts, which dates to around 350 CE, but this information is supplemented by various heresiological writings by early proto-orthodox theologians, most significantly Irenaeus, who wrote around 180 CE.

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Most of what we know about this group derives from the discovery of the Nag Hammadi collection of Coptic manuscripts, which dates to around 350 CE, but this information is supplemented by various heresiological writings by early proto-orthodox theologians, most significantly Irenaeus, who wrote around 180 CE.

↳ Are they oral:

— No

Notes: They may have had oral texts, but there is no surviving evidence of such.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

— Yes

Notes: There does seem to be a central Sethian myth, which no single text preserves in its entirety. Some features of the Sethian myth include: (1) an ineffable divine first principle called the Parent or Invisible Spirit; (2) a second principle called Barbelo; (3) a series of four luminaries, also called aeons or realms, named Harmozel, Oroiael, Daveithai, and Eleleth; (4) the emanation of a number of additional aeons, the last of which is named Wisdom (Sophia in Greek); (5) a craftsman (dēmiourgos in Greek) named Ialdabaoth, who steals divine power from his mother (Wisdom) to create the visible cosmos based on intelligible paradigms while remaining ignorant of the divinities higher than him; (6) the creation of seven, twelve, and/or 365 rulers of the material world who themselves create human beings and the remainder of the material world; (7) a dramatic struggle resulting in some of humanity being given Ialdabaoth's pilfered power as a spark of divinity; (8) these human beings are the offspring of Seth, sealed by a special baptismal ritual, while the offspring of Cain remain under the power of the ignorant demiurge and his minions. (9) Where the human Jesus appears in the versions of this myth, he is variously identified with a preexistent Anointed One (Greek christos), a preexistent Word (Greek logos), a preexistent Seth, or Barbelo.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

— No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

— Yes

Notes: The Three Steles of Seth are ostensibly a text revealed by the preexistent Seth (as a divine aeon or realm) to an unnamed human author.

↳ Inspired by high god:

— No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

— Yes

Notes: The distinction between revelation and inspiration is hard to infer from the texts. The Three Steles of Seth are ostensibly a text revealed (or inspired) by the preexistent Seth (as a divine aeon or realm) to an unnamed human author.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

— Yes

Notes: It is implied that some of the Sethian texts are given to human beings in written

form (The Three Steles of Seth). The distinction between revealed, inspired, and originated is difficult to ascertain from the surviving material.

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably all of the texts had a human author, even if they were inspired or revealed by divine or semi-divine beings.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Sethians would have been in contact with other Christian groups and with a variety of non-Christian religions in the Roman Empire.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Given the heresiological disputes beginning in the late second century CE, there was undoubtedly competition between different Christian groups.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, it must have been, but there isn't a lot of information.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, it must have been, but there isn't a lot of information.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are stories (e.g., martyrdom accounts) of violence against Christian groups by non-Christians. However, there are no recorded cases of someone specifically identified as a "Sethian" (or a "gnostic") who was martyred or the target of any other violence.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are some recorded instances of violence between Christians and non-Christians, but whether these events would have included Sethians is unknown.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: No surviving archaeological evidence of that scale exists for the Sethians.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 12000

Notes: It is impossible to say how many adherents there were based on only the textual evidence that survives, but the number must have been very small. The estimate of 12,000 Sethians in 200 CE should be considered speculative at best (there exists no ancient census data), and based on the following reasoning. Sociologist Rodney Stark (in *The Rise of Christianity*, 1996), by projecting an exponential growth curve over the estimated population of the Roman empire, estimates that there were roughly 200,000 Christians in the year 200. If 2-10% of this number were Sethian (or varieties of Sethian), we might expect 4000-20,000 Sethians in 200 CE. Many (if not most) scholars would find this reasoning spurious. The notion of a smooth exponential growth curve of Christianity based on the analogy of Mormonism growing 43% each decade in the 20th century (in Stark's account) is highly problematic, if for no other reasons than Mormonism was not illegal in that period, nor has it ever become the officially sanctioned religion of an empire. As proto-orthodox Christianity became more and more entrenched in the 3rd and 4th centuries, Sethians would have been increasingly persecuted. It is not a coincidence that the Nag Hammadi Library of texts were found stashed in a cave in Upper Egypt, where a Christian monk felt compelled to hide them. Hence the chosen date of 200 CE, which, if there was ever a "flourishing" of Sethianism, may have fallen around that date. To apply the same reasoning to 150 CE, when Stark estimates 40,000 Christians, the Sethians may have numbered around 800-4000.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: The Baptismal Ritual of the Five Seals (see below).

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Membership in the group was presumably voluntary, but formalized by an elaborate baptismal ritual.

Assigned by class:

– No

Assigned at a specific age:

– Field doesn't know

Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: There is significant textual evidence for a Sethian ritual of baptism sometimes called a ritual of “five seals.” See specifically the Apocryphon of John (NHC II 31:22); Trimorphic Protennoia 48:30, 49:27, 50:9; and Gospel of the Egyptians 56:25.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: No surviving archaeological evidence of that scale exists for the Sethians.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.02

Notes: Using the same (unavoidably problematic) reasoning in the question above, the Roman Empire may have been 0.02% Sethian in 200 CE, based on an estimated population of 60 million.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The use of texts written to be read aloud to listeners implies that proselytizing was significant.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Probably recommended for those who were literate and able to read scripture aloud.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– I don't know

Notes: There doesn't seem to be any evidence of missionary work, but given the missionary imperative of Christianity in general, it may have occurred.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: Joining the Sethians was voluntary, or at least there is no evidence to the contrary.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Definitely no, neither from the Roman Empire, nor from the proto-orthodox Christian hierarchy.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: This is a qualified yes. Some iconography exists on gems from late antiquity, but the figures represented are shared between different traditions (Sethian, "magical," etc.).

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

Notes: This is a qualified yes. Some jewelry has survived from this period with iconography that has been described as "gnostic," but the figures portrayed are shared with other traditions, e.g. Abrasax who appears also in the Greek Magical Papyri (PGM).

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Ialdabaoth, the ignorant creator god, is sometimes portrayed as a lion-headed serpent. Some iconography exists on gems from late antiquity, but the figures represented are shared between different traditions (Sethian, "magical," etc.). Abrasax, for example, is sometimes also portrayed as a lion-headed serpent.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

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portrayed in a variety of forms, sometimes as a human child seated upon a lotus flower (borrowing the iconography of the Egyptian Harpocrates, i.e. Horus the Child).

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: Some divine forms are addressed by strings of Greek vowels, sometimes arranged in an implied pyramid formation, as in the Holy Book of the Great Invisible Spirit (Gospel of the Egyptians).

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

Notes: There is no existing evidence for this.

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Some divine forms are addressed by strings of Greek vowels, sometimes arranged in an implied pyramid formation, as in the Holy Book of the Great Invisible Spirit (Gospel of the Egyptians). Some scholars associate these vowels with the seven planetary spheres, which may indicate their use in rituals of ascent.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: Apostates are not punished by the community (presumably), but to willfully turn away from the gnosis after being initiated was vilified in the texts.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: No surviving archaeological evidence of that scale exists for the Sethians, but we cannot say definitively that they did not have sacred sites.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No information exists for Sethian sacred sites.

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

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Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

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↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

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Notes: The Three Steles of Seth are ostensibly a text revealed by the preexistent Seth (as a divine aeon or realm) to an unnamed human author.

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↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably all of the texts had a human author, even if they were inspired or revealed by divine or semi-divine beings.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: No surviving archaeological evidence of that scale exists for the Sethians.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: No surviving archaeological evidence of that scale exists for the Sethians.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: This is a qualified yes. Some iconography exists on gems from late antiquity, but the figures represented are shared between different traditions (Sethian, "magical," etc.).

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

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↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Ialdabaoth, the ignorant creator god, is sometimes portrayed as a lion-headed serpent. Some iconography exists on gems from late antiquity, but the figures represented are shared between different traditions (Sethian, "magical," etc.). Abrasax, for example, is sometimes also portrayed as a lion-headed serpent.

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Notes: Some divine forms are addressed by strings of Greek vowels, sometimes arranged in an implied pyramid formation, as in the Holy Book of the Great Invisible Spirit (Gospel of the Egyptians).

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

Notes: There is no existing evidence for this.

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Some divine forms are addressed by strings of Greek vowels, sometimes arranged in an implied pyramid formation, as in the Holy Book of the Great Invisible Spirit (Gospel of the Egyptians). Some scholars associate these vowels with the seven planetary spheres, which may indicate their use in rituals of ascent.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: No surviving archaeological evidence of that scale exists for the Sethians, but we cannot say definitively that they did not have sacred sites.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No information exists for Sethian sacred sites.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: It is present and quite prominent. The physical body is often referred to as a prison, shackle, or garment.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The physical body is often referred to as a prison, shackle, or garment. The divine spark of intellect or spirit is what is capable of salvation.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: This is true generally of the Middle Platonic background shared by Sethians, Philo of Alexandria, and many other religious movements of this period.

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Asceticism of various forms was practiced by most early Christians and the Sethians were no exception.

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Some versions of the Sethian myth present a dramatic struggle resulting in some of humanity being given Ialdabaoth's pilfered power as a spark of divinity; these human beings are the offspring of Seth, sealed by a special baptismal ritual, while the offspring of Cain remain under the power of the ignorant demiurge and his minions. Where the human Jesus appears in the versions of this myth, he is variously identified with a preexistent Anointed One (Greek christos), a preexistent Word (Greek logos), a preexistent Seth, or Barbelo.

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: There are many supernatural beings present in a complex hierarchy.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: He/it is described as the father/parent or Great Invisible Spirit and is sometimes characterized as androgynous.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The Great Invisible Spirit lacks qualities in general (negative theology) or is characterized by paradox (possessing both sexes, etc.).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Only in a very indirect way, through emanation of all divine beings, as well as the progenitor of the "immovable race" of Seth.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Notes: This is ambiguous. For Plato, the supreme high god was by definition good, but later Platonists (e.g. Numenius) who were influential on the Sethians denied the highest

deity even this quality.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– No

Notes: There is no unambiguous indication of this, but there is a spark of the highest deity within the chosen, so perhaps knowledge may be possible.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, through a complex system of emanation, but this must be inferred. The Great Invisible Spirit (or "Parent of the Entirety") is the source of everything that exists, and there are numerous examples of lower divine beings interacting causally with the world. For example, Sophia (Wisdom) gives birth to Ialdabaoth, the ignorant creator deity, who subsequently creates the material world and the archons who preside over fate. See the helpful diagram on pp. 12-13 of Layton, *The Gnostic Scriptures*, 1987.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but those permissible to worship are understood to be emanations of the supreme high god.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

— No

Notes: The Great Invisible Spirit doesn't communicate with the living, unless one infers that as the "parent of the entirety" and ultimate source of all that exists, the Spirit is the ultimate cause of the existence of the Sethian scriptures, which are themselves a form of "communication." A series of salvific intermediaries (Barbelo, Sophia, Seth, the Christ) communicate with the living in the various revelation stories.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

— No

Notes: This is perhaps implied, given the salvation of the chosen and their escape from the cycle of reincarnation, but it is never explicitly stated.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

— Yes

Notes: The Sethian myth includes a complex system of emanation which creates a divine hierarchy. Some features of the Sethian myth include: (1) an ineffable divine first principle called the Parent or Invisible Spirit; (2) a second principle called Barbelo; (3) a series of four luminaries, also called aeons or realms, named Harmozel, Oroiael, Daveithai, and Eleleth; (4) the emanation of a number of additional aeons, the last of which is named Wisdom (Sophia in Greek); (5) a craftsman (dēmiourgos in Greek) named Ialdabaoth, who steals divine power from his mother (Wisdom) to create the visible cosmos based on intelligible paradigms while remaining ignorant of the divinities higher than him; (6) the creation of seven, twelve, and/or 365 rulers of the material world who themselves create human beings and the remainder of the material world; (7) a dramatic struggle resulting in some of humanity being given Ialdabaoth's pilfered power as a spark of divinity; (8) these human beings are the offspring of Seth, sealed by a special baptismal ritual, while the offspring of Cain remain under the power of the ignorant demiurge and his minions. (9) Where the human Jesus appears in the versions of this myth, he is variously identified with a preexistent Anointed One (Greek christos), a preexistent Word (Greek logos), a preexistent Seth, or Barbelo.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

— No

Notes: Qualified No: Some supernatural beings are identified with the visible stars and planets, so those can be seen.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

— No

Notes: The possible exception would include the lowest supernatural beings who may have had bodies of pneuma (breath). This is true of contemporary Platonist and Hermetic movements, which are closely related in some ways to Sethianism.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them take an active interest in the salvation of this world. These beings include Sophia (Wisdom), the preexistent Anointed One (Greek christos), the preexistent Word (Greek logos), the preexistent Seth, and Barbelo (in various versions of the Sethian myth).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Perhaps, but there seems to be no unambiguous evidence of this.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: This is only an yes by implication that the status of the saved (the Seed/Offspring of Seth) has a different metaphysical status.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: They will know this with regard to whether the individual is saved, i.e. belongs to the Seed/Offspring of Seth.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The descent of various figures (Seth, Sophia, Jesus, etc.) is presented as the key to salvation (which also manifests in baptism).

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The descent of various figures (Seth, Sophia, Jesus, etc.) is presented as the key to salvation (which also manifests in baptism).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: This is an implied yes. Members of the Seed of Cain (the unsaved) are condemned to the cycle of reincarnation and the shackle of the mortal body.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: This is true through the complex system of emanation present in Sethian myth.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Notes: There is some slight ambiguity here, in that the descending savior figures desire to save humanity and achieve their goals.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them exhibit negative emotions such as jealousy. Ialdabaoth specifically echoes the passages of Jewish scripture indicating he is jealous or ignorant of the divine powers above him.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: Caveat: If desire or the sense of their own lack can be considered a kind of "hunger," then yes.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Some of the supernatural beings (the cosmic rulers) possess lust (for Eve and possibly other human women).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There is a complex hierarchy of divine beings. These include invisible (noetic or spiritual) beings or "realms" (aeons) as well as lower entities who are identified with various elements of the visible cosmos, such as stars and planets.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: In limited cases, yes. For example, Sophia (Wisdom) is presented as the mother of Ialdabaoth (in some texts). Sometimes emanation is presented metaphorically as a kind of sexual generation.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: The hierarchy includes (but is not exhausted by) the following list: (1) an ineffable divine first principle called the Parent or Invisible Spirit; (2) a second principle called Barbelo; (3) a series of four luminaries, also called aeons or realms, named Harmozel, Oroiael, Daveithai, and Eleleth; (4) the emanation of a number of additional aeons, the last of which is named Wisdom (Sophia in Greek); (5) a craftsman (dēmiourgos in Greek) named Ialdabaoth, who steals divine power from his mother (Wisdom) to create the visible cosmos based on intelligible paradigms while remaining ignorant of the divinities higher than him; (6) the creation of seven, twelve, and/or 365 rulers of the material world who themselves create human beings and the remainder of the material world.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases yes. The world rulers (created by Ialdabaoth) sometimes have power over specific parts of the cosmos or specific parts of the human body.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Those who were saved would escape the cycle of reincarnation and ascend to the immortal aeons.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: In the Middle Platonic context, nothing outside (or ontologically prior to) the visible/material world exists in time or space.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The conventions of the Roman Empire were vastly different from Christian morality in general, and the Sethian Christians were no exception to this.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is often not explicit in Sethian texts, but is implied.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Ialdabaoth and other cosmic rulers exhibit sexual lust for Eve, implying that sexual lust in general is a source of suffering.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Caveat: Only in the sense that all material life is an ongoing punishment in the shackle of the body.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Those who had not (yet) received gnosis and salvific baptism were doomed to the cycle of reincarnation in the shackle of the material body.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably this is possible (in animal form at least) among some Sethian texts, but there is very little evidence for it. Some Middle Platonic and Neopythagorean thinkers who influenced Sethianism thought it was possible though.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

Notes: There is no notion of karma or anything similar, although there are notions of Fate operative in Christianity in general. However, in Sethianism the individual will is emphasized and baptism had the power to overcome Fate (Greek heimarmene).

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: Caveat: Only in the sense that all material life is an ongoing punishment in the shackle of the body, and that escaping the cycle of reincarnation is a reward. However, this is ultimately dependent on human volition.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: There is no surviving evidence for this.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: There is no surviving evidence for this.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: There is no surviving evidence for this.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: There is no surviving evidence for this.

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: It is present and quite prominent. The physical body is often referred to as a prison, shackle, or garment.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The physical body is often referred to as a prison, shackle, or garment. The divine spark of

intellect or spirit is what is capable of salvation.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: This is true generally of the Middle Platonic background shared by Sethians, Philo of Alexandria, and many other religious movements of this period.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Those who were saved would escape the cycle of reincarnation and ascend to the immortal aeons.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: In the Middle Platonic context, nothing outside (or ontologically prior to) the visible/material world exists in time or space.

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Notes: There is no surviving evidence for this.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: There is no surviving evidence for this.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: There are many supernatural beings present in a complex hierarchy.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: He/it is described as the father/parent or Great Invisible Spirit and is sometimes characterized as androgynous.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The Great Invisible Spirit lacks qualities in general (negative theology) or is characterized by paradox (possessing both sexes, etc.).

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: Only in a very indirect way, through emanation of all divine beings, as well as the progenitor of the "immovable race" of Seth.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Notes: This is ambiguous. For Plato, the supreme high god was by definition good, but later Platonists (e.g. Numenius) who were influential on the Sethians denied the highest deity even this quality.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– No

Notes: There is no unambiguous indication of this, but there is a spark of the highest deity within the chosen, so perhaps knowledge may be possible.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, through a complex system of emanation, but this must be inferred. The Great Invisible Spirit (or "Parent of the Entirety") is the source of everything that exists, and there are numerous examples of lower divine beings interacting causally with the world. For example, Sophia (Wisdom) gives birth to Ialdabaoth, the ignorant creator deity, who subsequently creates the material world and the archons who preside over fate. See the helpful diagram on pp. 12-13 of Layton, *The Gnostic Scriptures*, 1987.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

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↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

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↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but those permissible to worship are understood to be emanations of the supreme high god.

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↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

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Notes: The Great Invisible Spirit doesn't communicate with the living, unless one infers that as the "parent of the entirety" and ultimate source of all that exists, the Spirit is the ultimate cause of the existence of the Sethian scriptures, which are themselves a form of "communication." A series of salvific intermediaries (Barbelo, Sophia, Seth, the Christ) communicate with the living in the various revelation stories.

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Notes: This is perhaps implied, given the salvation of the chosen and their escape from the cycle of reincarnation, but it is never explicitly stated.

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Notes: The Sethian myth includes a complex system of emanation which creates a divine hierarchy. Some features of the Sethian myth include: (1) an ineffable divine first principle called the Parent or Invisible Spirit; (2) a second principle called Barbelo; (3) a series of four luminaries, also called aeons or realms, named Harmozel, Oroiael, Daveithai, and Eleleth; (4) the emanation of a number of additional aeons, the last of which is named Wisdom (Sophia in Greek); (5) a craftsman (dēmiourgos in Greek) named Ialdabaoth, who steals divine power from his mother (Wisdom) to create the visible cosmos based on intelligible paradigms while remaining ignorant of the divinities higher than him; (6) the creation of seven, twelve, and/or 365 rulers of the material world who themselves create human beings and the remainder of the material world; (7) a dramatic struggle resulting in some of humanity being given Ialdabaoth's pilfered power as a spark of divinity; (8) these human beings are the offspring of Seth, sealed by a special baptismal ritual, while the offspring of Cain remain under the power of the ignorant demiurge and his minions. (9) Where the human Jesus appears in the versions of this myth, he is variously identified with a preexistent Anointed One (Greek christos), a preexistent Word (Greek logos), a preexistent Seth, or Barbelo.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

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Notes: Qualified No: Some supernatural beings are identified with the visible stars and planets, so those can be seen.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

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Notes: The possible exception would include the lowest supernatural beings who may have had bodies of pneuma (breath). This is true of contemporary Platonist and Hermetic movements, which are closely related in some ways to Sethianism.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

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Notes: Some of them take an active interest in the salvation of this world. These beings include Sophia (Wisdom), the preexistent Anointed One (Greek christos), the preexistent Word (Greek logos), the preexistent Seth, and Barbelo (in various versions of the Sethian myth).

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– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Perhaps, but there seems to be no unambiguous evidence of this.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: This is only an yes by implication that the status of the saved (the Seed/Offspring of Seth) has a different metaphysical status.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: They will know this with regard to whether the individual is saved, i.e. belongs to the Seed/Offspring of Seth.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The descent of various figures (Seth, Sophia, Jesus, etc.) is presented as the key to salvation (which also manifests in baptism).

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The descent of various figures (Seth, Sophia, Jesus, etc.) is presented as the key to salvation (which also manifests in baptism).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: This is an implied yes. Members of the Seed of Cain (the unsaved) are condemned to the cycle of reincarnation and the shackle of the mortal body.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: This is true through the complex system of emanation present in Sethian myth.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Notes: There is some slight ambiguity here, in that the descending savior figures desire to save humanity and achieve their goals.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Some of them exhibit negative emotions such as jealousy. Ialdabaoth specifically echoes the passages of Jewish scripture indicating he is jealous or ignorant of the divine powers above him.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: Caveat: If desire or the sense of their own lack can be considered a kind of "hunger," then yes.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Some of the supernatural beings (the cosmic rulers) possess lust (for Eve and possibly other human women).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There is a complex hierarchy of divine beings. These include invisible (noetic or spiritual) beings or "realms" (aeons) as well as lower entities who are identified with various elements of the visible cosmos, such as stars and planets.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: In limited cases, yes. For example, Sophia (Wisdom) is presented as the mother of Ialdabaoth (in some texts). Sometimes emanation is presented metaphorically as a kind of sexual generation.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: The hierarchy includes (but is not exhausted by) the following list: (1) an ineffable divine first principle called the Parent or Invisible Spirit; (2) a second principle called Barbelo; (3) a series of four luminaries, also called aeons or realms, named Harmozel, Oroiael, Daveithai, and Eleleth; (4) the emanation of a number of additional aeons, the last of which is named Wisdom (Sophia in Greek); (5) a craftsman (dēmiourgos in Greek) named Ialdabaoth, who steals divine power from his mother (Wisdom) to create the visible cosmos based on intelligible paradigms while remaining ignorant of the divinities higher than him; (6) the creation of seven, twelve, and/or 365 rulers of the material world who themselves create human beings and the remainder of the material world.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases yes. The world rulers (created by Ialdabaoth) sometimes have power over specific parts of the cosmos or specific parts of the human body.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Caveat: Only in the sense that all material life is an ongoing punishment in the shackle of the body.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: Caveat: Only in the sense that all material life is an ongoing punishment in the shackle of the body, and that escaping the cycle of reincarnation is a reward. However, this is ultimately dependent on human volition.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Some versions of the Sethian myth present a dramatic struggle resulting in some of humanity being given Ialdabaoth's pilfered power as a spark of divinity; these human beings are the offspring of Seth, sealed by a special baptismal ritual, while the offspring of Cain remain under the power of the ignorant demiurge and his minions. Where the human Jesus appears in the versions of this myth, he is variously identified with a preexistent Anointed One (Greek *christos*), a preexistent Word (Greek *logos*), a preexistent Seth, or Barbelo.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Asceticism of various forms was practiced by most early Christians and the Sethians were no exception.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The conventions of the Roman Empire were vastly different from Christian morality in general, and the Sethian Christians were no exception to this.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Strongly present and highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is often not explicit in Sethian texts, but is implied.

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

Notes: Ialdabaoth and other cosmic rulers exhibit sexual lust for Eve, implying that sexual lust in general is a source of suffering.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Presumably not, but celibacy would be recommended.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: If they follow Saint Paul's recommendations, then yes.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: If they follow Saint Paul's recommendations, then yes.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Abstinence is recommended for all.

Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Notes: Abstinence is recommended for all.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: If they follow the Jewish law, then perhaps, but this is not clear from the Sethian texts themselves.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Caveat: There is some textual evidence from hostile sources (proto-orthodox writers trying to discredit their enemies) that some later groups that were influenced by the Sethians (e.g. the Borborites) practiced child sacrifice, the consumption of sexual fluids, and so on. Scholars mostly agree that these are legends invented to discredit.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Caveat: If martyrdom is understood as self-sacrifice, then a qualified yes. Martyrdom would only be required (or rather, expected) under certain extreme conditions of persecution.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Caveat: Some Christians took a vow of poverty. This may have been true of some Sethian groups.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Caveat: The language of "required" is too strong, but it may very well have been expected that members spend time praying, attending services, and so on.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: In some sense, yes. In the greater context of early Christianity, members would be expected not to sin.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: There is very little evidence for this, but there were baptismal rituals, an implied communal meal, and some liturgical elements of Sethian texts (e.g. the Three Steles of Seth and the Gospel of the Egyptians). But whether members would have been "required" to attend this rituals is unknown.

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Caveat: It's not impossible that some Sethians may have followed the Jewish Law, requiring circumcision.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Initiates are members of the Seed (Offspring) of Seth, also called the Immoveable Race. Non-initiates are the Seed of Cain.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Initiates are members of the Seed (Offspring) of Seth, also called the Immoveable Race. Non-initiates are the Seed of Cain.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Presumably not, but celibacy would be recommended.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: If they follow Saint Paul's recommendations, then yes.

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: If they follow Saint Paul's recommendations, then yes.

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Abstinence is recommended for all.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Notes: Abstinence is recommended for all.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: If they follow the Jewish law, then perhaps, but this is not clear from the Sethian texts themselves.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Caveat: There is some textual evidence from hostile sources (proto-orthodox writers trying to discredit their enemies) that some later groups that were influenced by the Sethians (e.g. the Borborites) practiced child sacrifice, the consumption of sexual fluids, and so on. Scholars mostly agree that these are legends invented to discredit.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Caveat: If martyrdom is understood as self-sacrifice, then a qualified yes. Martyrdom would only be required (or rather, expected) under certain extreme conditions of persecution.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Caveat: Some Christians took a vow of poverty. This may have been true of some Sethian groups.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Caveat: The language of "required" is too strong, but it may very well have been expected that members spend time praying, attending services, and so on.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: In some sense, yes. In the greater context of early Christianity, members would be expected not to sin.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: There is very little evidence for this, but there were baptismal rituals, an implied communal meal, and some liturgical elements of Sethian texts (e.g. the Three Steles of Seth and the Gospel of the Egyptians). But whether members would have been "required" to attend this rituals is unknown.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Caveat: It's not impossible that some Sethians may have followed the Jewish Law, requiring circumcision.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Initiates are members of the Seed (Offspring) of Seth, also called the Immovable Race. Non-initiates are the Seed of Cain.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Initiates are members of the Seed (Offspring) of Seth, also called the Immovable Race. Non-initiates are the Seed of Cain.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The group existed within the Roman Empire, but it was certainly not an imperial religion.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: They probably lacked the financial means, but there is otherwise no evidence one way or the other.

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this one way or the other.

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: There seems to be some evidence of communal meals.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: There were Roman and Egyptian calendars not specific to the religious group.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There may have been a rare exception when a member of the Roman military was a Sethian Christian.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In certain contexts (large cities), the populace may have been supplied with a minimum of grain.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that local administrators had granaries that provided food storage, but whether this is "public" (and in what sense) is highly debatable.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes would have been levied by the imperial government and local administrators.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: There may have been rare exceptions for wealthy adherents of Sethian Christianity.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Local policing forces would have existed in the various cities of the Roman Empire, but they probably varied considerably from place to place.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There were Roman and Egyptian calendars not specific to the religious group.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, although the literacy rate would have been very low.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: It is certainly possible that some adherents may have interacted with bureaucracies within the Roman Empire.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would suggest this.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman military would have been more or less present in most cities.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence one way or the other, but it seems unlikely.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The religious specialists wrote mostly in Greek, and the translators of the Nag Hammadi texts wrote in Coptic.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In Egypt in certain municipalities near the Nile River, it is probable that irrigation and flood control were managed by the local temples.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Various officials of the Roman Empire may have acted as judges or appointed temporarily as such.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this one way or the other.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Wealthy adherents may have had access to transportation options within the Roman Empire. The Empire was certainly well known for its network of roads.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than

the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire had an elaborate legal code.

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The group existed within the Roman Empire, but it was certainly not an imperial religion.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: They probably lacked the financial means, but there is otherwise no evidence one way or the other.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: There may have been rare exceptions for wealthy adherents of Sethian Christianity.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: It is certainly possible that some adherents may have interacted with bureaucracies within the Roman Empire.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this one way or the other.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It is likely that local administrators had granaries that provided food storage, but whether this is "public" (and in what sense) is highly debatable.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would suggest this.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In Egypt in certain municipalities near the Nile River, it is probable that irrigation and flood control were managed by the local temples.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Wealthy adherents may have had access to transportation options within the Roman Empire. The Empire was certainly well known for its network of roads.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes would have been levied by the imperial government and local administrators.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Local policing forces would have existed in the various cities of the Roman Empire, but they probably varied considerably from place to place.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence one way or the other, but it seems unlikely.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Various officials of the Roman Empire may have acted as judges or appointed temporarily as such.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no written records or archaeological evidence that would indicate this one way or the other.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

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Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire would have exercised all manner of institutionalized punishments.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence to suggest this.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman Empire had an elaborate legal code.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There may have been a rare exception when a member of the Roman military was a Sethian Christian.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Roman military would have been more or less present in most cities.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, although the literacy rate would have been very low.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The religious specialists wrote mostly in Greek, and the translators of the Nag Hammadi texts wrote in Coptic.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: There were Roman and Egyptian calendars not specific to the religious group.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There were Roman and Egyptian calendars not specific to the religious group.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: There seems to be some evidence of communal meals.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In certain contexts (large cities), the populace may have been supplied with a minimum of grain.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)